

Parallel algorithm implementation for sparse matrix inversion

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Abstract—This paper describes the Gauss-Jordan method of calculating inverse matrices. An analysis of several papers on a similar topic is described, and the ways of performing the parallelization of Gauss-Jordan method for calculating inverse matrices. The achieved results of the related works are considered. An analysis of technologies suitable for parallel implementation of the calculation of inverse matrices of a rare type was performed, and the reasons why the CUDA platform is selected. Finally, the expected goals of the work itself are described.

Keywords—Graphics processing unit, Compute unified development architecture, Matrix inversion, Gauss Jordan, Parallelization.

I. INTRODUCTION

A simple implementation of a computation method that has no intrinsic parallelism consists of a sequence of operations to be performed (usually repeatedly) in order to obtain the solution. Unless the programming environment has special translation abilities, this is transformed into a single flow of processor instruction to be executed sequentially.

Common numerical algorithm implementations have little or no interaction with the computing environment, except for the data input and the result output. This means that the processing itself will be speed-bound by the speed at which the CPU can execute those instructions.

When multi-core and/or multi-processor technology is used to execute the program, this approach will use at most the capabilities of one processing core, leaving other resources unused. If the machine has other tasks to perform, this is acceptable from a global point of view, but still not optimal for the problem solving itself.

This work will show that relatively minor changes to a program can bring good improvement on processor usage, when the underlying algorithm offers the opportunity for parallel processing. [1]

Finding matrix inversion is a very important problem in the world of numerical algorithms – solving linear equations, structural analyses using finite element method, 3D rendering, digital filtering, image filtering and image processing – and constitutes an indispensable component in almost all mathematical/statistical software suites. [2]

There are several known methods like Gauss-Jordan, Strassen, Strassen-Newton, Cholesky decomposition, and Lower Upper Decomposition for matrix inversion.

The recursive nature of some matrix inversion algorithms such as Strassen-Newton reduces the effectiveness of parallelization. In recursive algorithms, each iteration needs to wait for the result of previous iteration. In Gauss-Jordan method, each iteration calculates the new values of all elements in the matrix that cause this method to be more appropriate for parallelization. GPUs has demonstrated high computing power in several application fields and GPUs can be used to speedup the Gauss-Jordan matrix inversion method. On the other hand, GPU also produces high power consumption and has been one of the largest power consumers in desktop and supercomputer systems. [3]

This work will consider inversion of sparse matrix type. In numerical analysis and scientific computing, a sparse matrix or sparse array is a matrix in which most of the elements are zero. There is no strict definition how many elements need to be zero for a matrix to be considered sparse but a common criterion is that the number of non-zero elements is roughly the number of rows or columns. [4]

II. CHARACTERISTICS OF SPARSE MATRIX INVERSION

A sparse matrix $[A]$ of size n , has the same number k of non-zero elements in each row(column) and it is assumed that $k \ll n$. Such systems occur in many applications.

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c & & & & c & b \\ b & a & b & c & & & & c \\ c & b & a & b & c & & & \\ & c & b & a & b & c & & \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & c & b & a & b & c \\ c & & & & c & b & a & b \\ b & c & & & & c & b & a \end{bmatrix}$$

Implementations in this work are modified versions of the basic Gaussian elimination algorithm. The matrix used is sparse, symmetric and positive definite.

$[A]$ matrix is symmetric if $[A] = [A]^T$, where $[A]^T$ is the transpose of $[A]$. In this work two important characteristics of sparse symmetric matrix inversion are used. Firstly, if $[A]$ is symmetric and positive definite, then $[A]^{-1}$ is also symmetric and positive definite. This identity matches the concept of Cholesky factorization. Therefore, the factorization steps can be continued without pivoting until the inversion is obtained.

Secondly, if $[A]$ is sparse, its inverse will not be sparse in general. Consequently, sparsity of a matrix does not reduce the storage requirements of its inverse. Based on the characteristics above, Gaussian elimination is identified as the most suitable method for the implementation of sparse symmetric matrix inversion. Since matrix $[A]$ is positive definite, it is unnecessary to do any parallel pivoting when the matrix is eliminated. This can save a lot of computation cost.

Furthermore, it is observed that each row in matrix $[A]^{-1}$ is a rearrangement of the vector $[d, e, f, \dots]$. The i -th row vector can be obtained by shifting the $(i + 1)$ -th row vector one to the left with wrap around. Therefore, by using Gaussian elimination, if matrix $[A]$ is reduced to the upper triangular matrix by row operations and these operations are applied simultaneously to identity matrix I , at last one row vector of matrix $[A]^{-1}$ can be obtained. Therefore, the last row can be used to generate the whole matrix $[A]^{-1}$ in parallel instead of further elimination or forward/backward substitution. [5]

$$[A]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} d & e & f & g & h & \dots & g & f & e \\ e & d & e & f & g & \dots & h & g & f \\ f & e & d & e & f & \dots & g & h & g \\ g & f & e & d & e & \dots & f & g & h \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & \\ g & h & g & f & e & \dots & d & e & f \\ f & g & h & g & f & \dots & e & d & e \\ e & f & g & h & g & \dots & f & e & d \end{bmatrix}$$

III. RELATED WORK

There has been much recent work decreasing the execution time of Gauss-Jordan method for matrix inversion. Some researchers focus on using multiple GPUs [6]. Although splitting the matrix between GPUs and ability to use them is important, in study [3] the focus is on one GPU, and a method that has a considerable reduction of the computational time and power consumption is proposed.

In [7], the inversion of large and dense matrices is studied, on hybrid CPU-GPU platforms, with application to the solution of matrix equations arising in control theory. Several matrix inversion algorithms are presented, based on common matrix factorizations and the GJE method, similar to [6], but for solving equations in control theory.

In [8], a parallel matrix inversion algorithm based on Gauss-Jordan elimination with pivoting is proposed. This method divides the matrix into some sub-matrices and assign each sub-matrices to one core. Each core updates the sub-matrix using Gauss-Jordan elimination. This method experimented in at most four cores and has communication overhead. Then, this method can not used in many core platforms such as GPU.

The method in [2] proposed a fast GPU-based Parallel Gauss-Jordan method (PGJM). This algorithm calculates the inverse of matrix in two steps using Gauss-Jordan method. Their method uses n and $n \times n - 1$ threads for steps 1 and 2, respectively. As the matrix size increases, the parallel Gauss-Jordan method will need more threads, blocks, streaming multiprocessors (SMs) and thus more processing cores. In addition, using more processing cores results more power consumption. Comparing to the method that proposed in [2], the method in [3] is using one step for calculating the inverse of matrix. The improved parallel Gauss-Jordan method (I-PGJM) is faster than PGJM. In fact, using different grid and block dimensions it can affect the power consumption. Thus, Some trade-off between the speed-up and power consumption of I-PGJM can be made.

IV. GAUSS-JORDAN ALGORITHM

In this section, the Gauss-Jordan matrix inversion method is reviewed. The algorithm starts with a square $n \times n$ matrix $[A]$. This matrix is augmented (right-extended) with an identity matrix of the same order into an extended matrix $[C]$.

$$[C] = [A|I] = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & \dots & a_{1n} & | & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{13} & \dots & a_{2n} & | & 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{13} & \dots & a_{3n} & | & 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & | & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & a_{n3} & \dots & a_{nn} & | & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Elementary row operations are used then to reduce the left half of $[C]$ occupied by $[A]$ into the identity matrix. Each iteration i for this step aims to reduce the a_{ii} element to 1

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} \ddots & \dots \\ \vdots & 1 & a_{i-1,i}^{(i-1)} & a_{i-1,i+1}^{(i-1)} & a_{i-1,i+2}^{(i-1)} & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & 0 & 1 & a_{i,i+1}^{(i-1)}/a_{i,i}^{(i-1)} & a_{i,i+2}^{(i-1)}/a_{i,i}^{(i-1)} & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & 0 & a_{i+1,i}^{(i-1)} & a_{i+1,i+1}^{(i-1)} & a_{i+1,i+2}^{(i-1)} & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \vdots \\ \dots & \ddots \end{bmatrix}$$

where a^k is the result of the iteration k . Further operation is to zero all a_{ji} coefficients except a_{ii} by replacing row j with a properly chosen linear combination between row i and row j .

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} \ddots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \vdots & 1 & 0 & a_{i-1,i+1}^{(i)} & a_{i-1,i+2}^{(i)} & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & 0 & 1 & a_{i,i+1}^{(i)} & a_{i,i+2}^{(i)} & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & 0 & 0 & a_{i+1,i+1}^{(i-1)} - a_{i,i+1}^{(i)} & a_{i+1,i+2}^{(i-1)} - a_{i,i+2}^{(i)}/a_{i+1,i}^{(i-1)} & \vdots & \vdots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \ddots & \ddots \end{bmatrix}$$

After all iterations are over, the right half of $[C]$ will contain $[A]^{-1}$.

$$[C] = \left[\begin{array}{cccc|cccc} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & a_{1,1}^{\{inv\}} & a_{1,2}^{\{inv\}} & \dots & a_{n,n}^{\{inv\}} \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 & a_{2,1}^{\{inv\}} & a_{2,2}^{\{inv\}} & \dots & a_{2,n}^{\{inv\}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 & a_{n,1}^{\{inv\}} & a_{n,2}^{\{inv\}} & \dots & a_{n,n}^{\{inv\}} \end{array} \right]$$

Iterations have to be performed sequentially, i.e. iteration $k + 1$ has to be performed after iteration k is over. However, the algorithm has some opportunities for parallel processing.

The first step of the iteration i means dividing all elements of row i with a_{ii} and this can be executed in parallel. However, the simple division is an operation too simple compared to the overhead implied by parallelism introduction and the gains would be rather small.

The second step of iteration i is performed over all rows j with $j = i$ and within each row j one multiplication and one addition has to be performed for each column of the rows i and j . Processing one row j is an operation complex enough to allow parallel processing despite parallelization overhead. Moreover, particular programming techniques allow us to reduce the overhead to one equivalent fork/join operation per iteration i . [1]

V. PARALLEL IMPLEMENTATION

The algorithm is redesigned to exploit the capabilities of GPU parallel processing. Steps 1 and 2 are performed in parallel, i.e. for Step 1, spawn n threads and process the whole row at once, which can be implemented in CUDA C. For Step 2, $n \times (n - 1)$ threads are spawned to convert the rest of the column to 0 which can be implemented in CUDA C.

The computations are minimized by processing only the first n columns (starting from the j -th column) in the Step 2 instead of processing all the $2n$ columns. This will reduce the computations to half without affecting the final result, since for the columns after the $(n + j)$ -th column, the elements above the j -th row are still zero, hence they will not contribute to the step as the product will become zero. A further speed boost is obtained when the program is run using shared memory. Shared memory is a local common memory available to all the threads of the same thread block. Data read and write on shared memory is faster than that from GPU global memory making the shared memory act like a cache for the GPU. Thus, subject to availability of computational resources, the time complexity becomes proportional to $O(n)$.

As shown in algorithm 1, pivoting is done to prevent division by zero exception. While pivoting can be done inside the second for thread loop using conditional statement, it is done prematurely for all elements to avoid extra GPU cycles being used in the conditional statement. [2]

Algorithm 1: Pseudo code explaining the Gauss Jordan algorithm for matrix inversion adapted to GPU computing. [2]

```

Read matrix
Initialize  $n$  to size of matrix
Initialize  $j$  to 0
while  $j < n$  do
    Find  $k$  where  $matrix[k][j]$  is not 0
    Spawn  $n$  threads in 1 block
    for thread  $i$  of  $n$  in block 1 do
        |  $matrix[j][i] = matrix[j][i] + matrix[k][i]$ 
    end
    Spawn  $n$  threads in 1 block
    for thread  $i$  of  $n$  in block 1 do
        |  $matrix[j][i] = matrix[j][i]/matrix[j][i]$ 
    end
    Spawn  $n$  threads each in  $n$  blocks
    for thread  $i$  of  $n$  in block  $r$  do
        |  $matrix[i][r] = matrix[i][r] -$ 
        |    $matrix[i][j] \times matrix[j][r]$ 
    end
    Increase  $j$  by 1
end
Write matrix

```

VI. RESULTS

Implementation and recording of the given algorithms and their results are done on a Hp ProBook 470 G5, laptop with a Core i7-8550U @1.99GHz, 4 Cores, 8 Threads 16GB of DDR4 2400MHz SDRAM and an NVidia GeForce 930MX GPU. The computer is running Windows 10 Pro.

After investigation a parallel implementation of inverse matrix calculation was found. After a lot of trials and testing no improvements were added to the existing implementation. Beside this, a naive implementation of sequential matrix inversion was implemented. This enabled a time comparison between the parallel and sequential implementation, (The results are shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3). In the results, it's noticeable that the sequential implementation is faster than the parallel in cases of smaller size matrices. And as the size of matrix exceeds 1000×1000 the time complexity jumps exponentially. All tests were done by generating sparse matrix as the initial data. This fact is important considering that sparse matrix is the most general matrix in case of problems involving structural analysis and this work is based, as said, on this type of matrices.

A method for generating a matrix of desired size was added. This method accepts two parameters which define how many zeros will the matrix have and if the elements above or below the diagonal will be zeros. For example, if the second parameter is sent $[1/ - 1]$ then the first parameter represents how many of the other side of the diagonal will be zeros. The rest of the elements are generated randomly. If no parameters are sent then $[A]$ sparse matrix is generated with random values

on random positions. In this work, 70 percent of the elements are set to zeros.

Size	Parallel (ms)	Sequential (ms)
20	135.17	1
32	133.469	1
50	133.612	2
64	139.298	3
100	137.559	13
128	136.708	23
256	148.103	157
260	144.479	277
280	142.9	244
300	156.366	312
320	142.566	384
350	147.533	397
400	152.701	619
450	161.241	866
512	171.394	1025
550	175.624	1644
600	185.171	2449
650	199.401	2592
700	206.27	3255
750	215.248	4084
800	232.39	5046
850	255.606	5719
900	268.787	7090

Fig. 1. Table representing execution time on GPU and CPU, for small matrix sizes

Fig. 2. Graph representing execution time on GPU and CPU

Size	Parallel (ms)	Sequential (ms)
1024	283.599	7888
1100	368.294	11223
1200	432.543	15791
1500	494.17	31631
1750	499.969	47904
2048	909.747	74420
4096	2850.53	474624
8192	54365	4688500
16384	462626	

Fig. 3. Table representing execution time parallel and sequential for a random sparse matrix

Acceleration achieved between parallel and sequential is 70.48 times.

Fig. 4. Graph representing execution time parallel and sequential for a random sparse matrix

Size	Parallel (ms)	Sequential (ms)
1024	188.796	7825
1100	224.075	11442
1200	286.129	17571
1500	514.948	30410
1750	797.622	49347
2048	1237.9	76460
4096	9197.68	632662
8192	71163.1	4321200
16384	581704	

Fig. 5. Table representing execution time parallel and sequential for a sparse matrix with all zeros above the diagonal

Acceleration achieved between parallel and sequential is 50.51 times.

Fig. 6. Graph representing execution time parallel and sequential for a sparse matrix with all zeros above the diagonal

Size	Parallel (ms)	Sequential (ms)
1024	182.187	8015
1100	222.952	11163
1200	273.643	16144
1500	514.683	30983
1750	702.369	50503
2048	1189.07	76210
4096	8353.14	673461
8192	70071.9	5558690
16384	576054	

Fig. 7. Table representing execution time parallel and sequential for a sparse matrix with all zeros under the diagonal

Acceleration achieved between parallel and sequential is 72.74 times.

Fig. 8. Graph representing execution time parallel and sequential for a sparse matrix with all zeros under the diagonal

Size	Parallel (ms)	Sequential (ms)
1024	291.566	7323
1100	336.851	9909
1200	394.257	13375
1500	567.597	24141
1750	751.473	37880
2048	942.283	60256
4096	4978.95	546296
8192	35764.9	4267200
16384	284247	

Fig. 9. Table representing execution time parallel and sequential for a ones matrix

Acceleration achieved between parallel and sequential is 39.28 times.

Fig. 10. Graph representing execution time parallel and sequential for a ones matrix

VII. CONCLUSION

The ability to invert large matrices accurately and quickly determines the effectiveness of a wide range of computational algorithms and products. It can be seen that the GPU implementation far outperforms the sequential implementation when it comes to large matrices. Large size matrices are usually common problems that scientists run into and these matrices are usually in form of sparse matrix. GPU computing is ideally suited for massively parallel tasks as the thread creation and memory transfer overheads are negligible. The implementation on sparse matrix of various sizes is tested, and it is shown that the time complexity of matrix inversion scales as n if enough computational resources are available. Linear scaling will continue by using a network of GPUs. It is also shown that GPU based parallel implementation for matrix inversion is orders of magnitude faster than CPU based parallel implementation. In future, GPUs availability will increase while the price drops.

From the results achieved, one thing that can be noticed is that the structure of matrix data matters to some extent when calculating the inverse matrix. For example, at smaller matrix sizes the matrices that have all zeros above or below

the diagonal are processed faster than a random sparse matrix. But when the data size starts growing so as the time of execution for these types of matrices (above diagonal or below the diagonal are all zeros). The same thing happens for the sequential code. The elementary matrix had the lowest time of execution and the reason for that is because a check if matrix is elementary matrix is added to just return that same matrix. The reason why it is added is that even though it increases the time execution is because the time added, cannot compare to the actual time of calculating matrix inversion. And when comparing added time to the actual time of matrix inversion it represents a c parameter in $cO(n)$ time complexity.

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